

PREDICTION OF TRANSIENT INSTABILITY ON 132KV TRANSMISSION GRID POWER SYSTEM USING TRAPEZOIDAL RULE.

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Abstract:

This paper deals with prediction of transient instability on 132kV grid network from Afam to Port Harcourt mains injection substation in Nigeria by determining the dynamic response of the generators on the system during fault conditions using Trapezoidal numerical technique. The network's data collected from Transmission Company of Nigeria were used as input to perform transient stability simulation in Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP 19.1) environment, so as to investigate the differential change in generator rotor angles, change in generator bus voltage and frequency of the system. Numerical techniques were deployed with circuit breaker and relay time setting (0.00, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, 0.10, 0.12, 0.14, 0.16, and 0.18.0.2s), when balanced 3 phase fault was initiated with the aim of determining the critical clearing angle (CCA) and critical clearing time (CCT) of the transmission grid. The results obtained shows that Trapezoidal rule numerical technique is stable, accurate, has a fast response time of 0.02s, lower percentage error of 5.6% and a stable critical clearing angle of 35.480. The Trapezoidal rule numerical technique is better when used compared to modified Euler method in sustaining stability during transient disturbance to the network under investigation when in operation.

Keywords: Transient Instability, Modified Euler, ETAP, Trapezoidal rule, Critical Clearing Angle, Critical Clearing Time.

I. INTRODUCTION

The stable operation of a power system ensures a continuous match between energy input going to the prime mover and output electrical energy taken out of the synchronous machine [1]. But, in developing countries like Nigeria, electricity demand outweighs the power generation capacity due to increase in population and quest for industrial growth. The rapidly increasing demand of electricity, can leads to the utilities operating the power transmission grid very close to its stability limit and the system may encounter disturbances as a result of load variations [2][3]. This could have a negative effect on the power system security if not adequately checked, it could result into partial or total system collapse scenarios with huge inconveniences and high cost to both utilities and consumers respectively [4]. Power system security indicates how secured is the power system under normal condition or with predicted contingency, and one of the vital indices to assess the security of a power system is the transient instability prediction [5] [6]. A power system is said to be transiently stable if it regains equilibrium after been subjected to disturbance involving large excursions of generator rotor angles, bus voltages, power flow, critical clearing angle, critical clearing time and other important system parameter responsible in assessing the power system stability [7]. The grid network in developing countries are faced with series of challenges like voltage instability, transmission line outages, occurrence of different type of faults, sudden loss of generator, high power losses and switching in and switching out loads, which creates

instability in the system, with lack of sensitive equipment to detect and stabilize these challenges, therefore, the importance of transient instability assessment and its prediction is very paramount in achieving a stable power system[8] [9].

In power system, the oscillatory relative motion between the rotor and synchronously rotating magnetic field of generators with time in case of any disturbance is expressed as Swing Equation, and it is a nonlinear second order differential equation. Therefore, it requires the usage of suitable integration numerical technique to determine an accurate approximate solution of the problem in order to assist the power system operators to take an adequate measure in carrying out physical or programmable actions to avert or reduce system collapse scenario.

II. Statement of the Problem

The study case 132kV transmission grid in Nigeria is fragile and highly stressed, with long and radial transmission line, and lack flexibility which may lead to instability or machine losses synchronism at the occurrence of fault. When voltage collapse occurs, it takes a longer time to restore power, therefore, has adverse effect on the socio-economic growth and industrialization in the area [10] [11]. Therefore, if the system must maintain a reliable service and remain intact, it should be capable of withstanding a variety of small and large disturbances in order to meet the task of wheeling all complex loads at normal operating condition. To cushion the effect of reoccurring system, collapse of the transmission network as a result of challenges associated with mismatch between power demanded and power supplied (overload), This research is proposing the usage of Trapezoidal rule technique for transient instability prediction, which will alert the operators to come up with several measures to avert system collapse as well as maintaining the system security and performance [12].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

• Stability in Power System

Stability of a power system is its ability to return to normal or stable operating conditions after having been subjected to some form of disturbance. Contrarily, instability means a condition denoting loss of synchronism when the system is subjected to disturbances. In addition, a system is adjudged to be stable (to stay in step), if the forces tending to hold machine in synchronism with one another are sufficient to overcome the disturbing forces [13].

Power is generated by synchronous machines that operate in synchronism with the rest of the system. A machine is said to synchronize with a bus when both of them have same frequency, voltage and phase sequence [14]. Power system stability is grouped into three, steady-state, dynamic, and transient stability.

Figure 1: Grouping of Power System Stability [15]

• **Transient Stability**

Transient stability is the ability of the power system to maintain synchronism when subject to a large and severe disturbances. The resulting system response to major disturbances which may cause large changes in generator rotor speeds, power transfers and rotor angles and is influenced by the non-linear power angle relationship. For a large disturbance, changes in angular difference may be so large as to cause the machine to fall out of step loss (synchronism)[16]. This will result to power, voltage and current to oscillate drastically which can cause damage to the system equipment and loads that receive power supply from the unstable system.

According to [17] they investigate the performance of a particle swarm optimization support vector machine (PSO-SVM) approach to transient stability analysis in the context of pre-fault control; the technique is implicated in such a way that the operating points of the power system are predicted and adjusted to secure the power system from consequent instability

According to [18] they investigated the transient stability performance of the Ikeja-West sub-transmission network of the Nigeria 330KV through a number of numerical fault simulation; for these set of simulations, the Electrical Transient Analysis Program (ETAP) software was used with the primary objective to determine the security limits of the case sub-transmission network. By redirecting the focus of transient stability studies towards a pre-fault response system such as the system is able to respond in milliseconds just before instability is induced

According to [19] they performed transient stability simulation studies taken into account balanced and unbalanced fault cases and comparing with different damping techniques with proposed technique. They examined the use of an optimal unified power flow controller (OUPFC) based on the Lyapunov energy function (LEF) for enhancement of the transient stability of a test power system. Their proposer OUPFC was compared to the standard Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) and they were able to report significant improvements, faster damping for the OUPFC consequently

IV. METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study is based on simulation and analysis. The study case system (132kV transmission network from Afam to Port Harcourt mains injection substation) was modelled in Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) environment for transient stability studies. The data collected from the operator was used as input into conventional swing equation method, and numerical integration methods such as Modified Euler and Trapezoidal rule for determining the transient behaviour of the test system when subjected to disturbance. Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 show load/transformer data, bus loading, network parameter and generation system parameter respectively.

Table 1: Load/ Transformer Data of the Network

Transmission Substation	Transmission Substation Location	Areas Connected 33KV Feeder	Load Connected (MW)	Transformer Location Name	Transformer Size (MVA)
Port Harcourt	Rumuobioakani	Abuloma	12	T _{1A}	60
		REF 1	10.5		
		RSPUB 2 REF 2	17.5		
			18		

Elekiah	14		
Uniport	25	T ₂ A	60
RSPUB 1 (Woji)	12		
FDR 3	18		
FDR 2	16	T ₃ A	60
Airport Feeder	24.5		

Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN)
Table 2: Bus Loading for the Transmission Network

Bus	MW (Max)	MW (Min)	MVAR (Max)	MVAR (Min)
T ₁ A	18	10.5	14.4	8.4
T ₂ A	25	12	20	9.6
T ₃ A	24.5	16	19.6	12.8

Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria, TCN
Table 3: Transmission Network Parameters

S/N	Parameters	Assigned Numerical Values
1.	H (G17&G18)	2.4816pu
	H(G19 & G20)	5.5969pu
	Total	8.08Pu
2.	MW (G17 & G18)	284.4MW
	MW (G19 & G20)	133MN
	Total	381MW
3.	Mechanical power	383MW
4.	Frequency (f)	50Hz
5.	Infinite Bus Voltage	1Pu

Table 4: Generation system parameters (Afam IV & V)

Bus	From	To
T ₁ A	Afam	Lumped Load on T ₁ A
T ₂ A	Afam	Lumped Load on T ₂ A
T ₃ A	Afam	Lumped Load on T ₃ A

• **Transient Stability Analysis Technique**

Figure 2: Equivalent Machine model

At stable pre-fault equilibrium points, the behaviour of synchronous machine under normal operating condition is given by:

$$\frac{Md^2\theta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) can be written as;

$$\frac{H}{\Pi f} \frac{d^2\delta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e(P_u) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is known the swing equation of a synchronous machine

Where:

H: Inertia constant

P_m: Input mechanical energy

P_e: Output electrical power

δ : Power angle

If there is a small disturbance of the rotor (Δ, δ), equation (2) becomes:

$$\frac{H}{\Pi f} \frac{d^2\delta}{dt^2} = \Delta P_m - \Delta P_e \quad (3)$$

Whereby the mechanical power of the generator is assumed to be constant equation (3) becomes:

$$\frac{H}{\Pi f} \frac{d^2\delta}{dt^2} = \Delta P_m(P_u) - P_e(P_u) \quad (4)$$

Putting maximum electrical power transfer into consideration, equation (4) can write as:

$$\frac{H}{\Pi f} \frac{d^2\delta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_{\max} \sin\delta \quad (5)$$

$$PS = \frac{dp}{d\delta} \text{ at } \delta_0, 0 = P_{\max} \cos\delta_0 \quad (6)$$

PS = P_{max} Cos δ₀ : The slope of the power angle curve at δ₀, Ps is positive when 0° < δ < 90°

Where:

PS: Shaft power

δ₀ : Initial operating angle of the machine

• **Calculation of Line Network Parameters using base of 250MVA**

$$P_e = \frac{381}{250} = 1.524P_u$$

$$P_m = \frac{383}{250} = 1.532P_u$$

$$X_{eq} = j0.275 + j0.097 + j0.0405$$

$$X_{eq} = j0.4125pu$$

$$\text{Complex power (S)} = \frac{Pe}{Pf} \angle \text{Cos}^{-1}(\theta)$$

Where Pf = $\theta = 0.8$

$$S = \frac{1.524}{0.8} [\text{Cos}^{-1}(0.8)] = 1.905 \angle -36.87^\circ$$

$$\text{Current, I} = \frac{S^*}{V^*} = \frac{1.905 \angle -36.87^\circ}{1.0 \angle 0} = 1.905 \angle -36.87^\circ$$

Excitation voltage, $E_g^1 = V + jX_d I$

$$E_g^1 = 1 \angle 0^\circ + (j0.4125) (1.905 \angle -36.87^\circ)$$

$$E_g^1 = 1 + j0 + 0.4715 + j0.6286$$

$$E_g^1 = 1.4715 + j0.6286$$

$$E_g^1 = 1.600 \angle 23.2^\circ \text{ pu.}$$

Initial operating power angle becomes:

$$\delta_0 = 23.20^\circ = 0.4049 \text{ rad}$$

Synchronous speed, $\omega_0 = 2 \pi f = 2 \pi \times 50 = 314.1593 \text{ rad/sec.}$

• **Application of swing equation Technique to Transient Stability.**

Substituting values into the swing equation (2);

$$\frac{H}{\pi f} \frac{d^2 \delta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e$$

$$\frac{8.08 d^2 \delta}{\pi \times 50 dt^2} = (1.532 - 0) \text{ during fault, } P_e = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2 \delta}{dt^2} = \frac{\pi \times 76.6}{8.08}$$

Integrating both sides

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \int \frac{\pi \times 76.6}{8.08} dt + 0$$

Integrating again

$$d\delta(t) = \frac{\pi \times 76.6}{16.16} t^2 + \delta_0$$

$$\delta(t) = \frac{\pi \times 76.6}{16.16} t^2 + 0.4049$$

At t = 0.02s, 1 cycle at 50Hz

$$\delta(0.02) = \frac{\pi \times 76.6}{16.16} (0.02)^2 + 0.4049 = \delta(0.02) = 0.4109 \text{ rad} \cong 23.54^\circ$$

The calculation is repeated for tenth cycles at time interval of 0.02 seconds

• **Application of Modified Euler Method Transient Stability**

Using the two conventional first order differential equations, the Modified Euler was used for investigation for ten cycle as:

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \omega_L - \omega_s \tag{7}$$

$$P_e \tag{8}$$

$$\frac{d\omega}{dt} = \frac{50\pi}{H} (P_m - P_e)$$

Where;

ω_L : Is the latest angular velocity

ω_s : Is the synchronous speed

δ_L : Is the latest torque angle

H : Is the inertial constant

P_m : Is the mechanical power

P_e : Is the electrical power

During fault condition $P_e = 0$

At t=0.02, 1st cycle:

First evaluation of $(\delta, \omega, \frac{d\delta}{dt})$

$$\frac{d\delta_1}{dt} = \omega_L - 314.1593$$

$$\frac{d\delta_1}{dt} = 314.1593 - 314.1593$$

$$\frac{d\delta_1}{dt} = 0$$

$$\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = 19.4405(1.532 - 0)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = 29.7828$$

Using the predictor equation for both results obtained using equations (7) and (8)

$$\delta_1(0.02) = \delta_L + \left(\frac{d\delta_1}{dt} \times \Delta t \right)$$

$$\delta_{1(0.02)} = 0.4049 + (0 \times 0.02)$$

$$\delta_1(0.02) = 0.4049 \text{ rad} = 23.2^\circ$$

$$\omega_1(0.02) = \omega_L + \left(\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} \times 0.02 \right)$$

$$\omega_1(0.02) = 314.1593 + (29.7828 \times 0.02)$$

$$\omega_1(0.02) = 314.1593 + 0.5957$$

$$\omega_1(0.02) = 314.755 \text{ rad/sec}$$

$$\omega_1 = \omega_r = 314.755 \text{ rad/sec}$$

Second evaluation of $(\delta, \omega, \frac{d\delta}{dt})$

$$\frac{d\delta_2}{dt} = \omega_r - 314.1593$$

$$\frac{d\delta_2}{dt} = 314.755 - 314.1593$$

$$\frac{d\delta_2}{dt} = 0.5957$$

$$\frac{d\omega_2}{dt} = 19.4405(1.532 - 0)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_2}{dt} = 29.7828$$

Applying the corrector equation to both first and second evaluation above

The corrector equation is given as:

$$\delta_2 = \delta_L + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\delta_1}{dt} + \frac{d\delta_2}{dt} \right) \times \Delta t$$

$$\delta_2 = 0.4049 + \frac{1}{2} (0 + 0.5957) \times 0.02$$

$$\delta_2 = 0.4049 + 5.957 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\delta_2 = 0.4049 \text{ rad} = 23.5^\circ$$

$$\omega_2 = \omega_L + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} + \frac{d\omega_2}{dt} \right) \times \Delta t$$

$$\omega_2 = 314.1593 + \frac{1}{2} (29.7828 + 29.7828) \times 0.02$$

$$\omega_2 = 314.1593 + 0.5957$$

$$\omega_2 = 314.755 \text{ rad/sec}$$

The calculations were repeated for ten cycles at time interval of 0.02 seconds.

• **Application of Trapezoidal Rule to Transient Stability.**

The general formular of the trapezoidal rule is as shown in equation Photovoltaic power generation system size can be evaluated as shown in equations (9) and (10).

$$\delta_{n+1} = \delta_L + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left(\frac{d\delta_n}{dt} + \frac{d\delta_{n+1}}{dt} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\omega_{n+1} = \omega_L + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left(\frac{d\omega_n}{dt} + \frac{d\omega_{n+1}}{dt} \right) \quad (10)$$

Where:

δ_{n+1} : Machine rotor angle evaluated at n+1

$\frac{d\omega_n}{dt}$: Differential Angular speed evaluated at n.

δ_L : Latest rotor angle

ω_{n+1} : Angular speed evaluated at n+1

$\frac{d\delta_n}{dt}$: Differential rotor angle evaluated at n.

ω_L : Latest angular speed

At t = 0.02s, 1st cycle at 50Hz

Input values into equations (9) and (10);

$$\delta_{(0.02)} = 0.4049 + \frac{1}{2}(0 + 0)$$

$$\delta_{(0.02)} = 0.4049 \text{ rad}$$

$$\frac{d\omega_0}{dt} = 19.4405(1.532 - 0) = 29.7828$$

$$\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = 29.7828$$

$$\omega_{(0.02)} = 314.1593 + \frac{0.02}{2}(29.7828 + 29.7828) = 314.7550 \text{ rad /sec.}$$

The calculations were repeated for ten cycles at time interval of 0.02 seconds.

• **Analysis of Error in Both Numerical Technique Solutions**

Mean absolute error is given as shown in equation (11);

$$\text{Mean absolute error (MAE)} = \frac{\sum (X_o - X)}{n} \tag{11}$$

Where:

n = is the serial number of errors

X_o = is the actual value

X = is the measure or calculated value

The conventional swing equation technique solution is taken as the actual value (X_o) and δ_o is considered to give the true representation of the rotor angles.

Table 5: Mean Absolute Error in the Solution of Rotor Angle at Incremental Time

Incremental Time	Conventional swing method δ (rad) X _o	Modified Euler δ (rad) = X ₁	Trapezoidal Rule δ (rad) = X ₂	Error in X ₁	Error in X ₂
0.02	0.4109	0.4109	0.4049	0	0.006
0.04	0.4287	0.4586	0.4109	-0.0299	0.0178
0.06	0.4585	0.6194	0.4288	-0.1609	0.0297
0.08	0.5202	1.0006	0.4586	-0.4804	0.0616
0.1	0.5538	1.7052	0.5003	-1.1514	0.0535
0.12	0.6193	2.9600	0.5539	-2.3407	0.0646
0.14	0.6968	4.9471	0.6194	-4.2503	0.0774
0.16	0.7361	7.9329	0.6968	-7.1968	0.0393
0.18	0.8874	12.2033	0.7862	-11.3159	0.1012
0.20	1.0006	18.0799	0.8875	-17.0793	0.1131
				-44.0056	0.5642

Percentage Mean Absolute Error using **Modified Euler method**

$$\% \text{ MAE} = \frac{44.0056}{10} \times 100 = -440$$

Percentage Mean Absolute Error using **Trapezoidal Rule method**

$$\% \text{ MAE} = \frac{0.5642}{10} \times 100 = 5.642$$

- **Estimation of the Critical Clearing Angle and Calculation of Critical Clearing Time**

The critical clearing time is calculated as show below [18]:

$$\text{Critical clearing time, } t_{cr} = \sqrt{(\delta_{cr} - \delta_0) \frac{4H}{W_s P_m}} \quad (12)$$

Where:

T_{cr} : Critical Clearing Time

δ_{cr} : Critical Clearing angle

W_o : Synchronous Speed

P_m : Mechanical Power

H : Inertia constant

If the relay is programmed to clear fault at 7 cycles, with the application of Trapezoidal rule, the rotor angle will reach 0.6194 radian (35.48°) which is less than 90° regions of instability. With Modified Euler, the rotor angle will reach 4.9471rad (283°), which is within the instability region.

To calculate critical clearing time for Trapezoidal rule solution, substituting values into equation (3.18)

$$t_{cr} = \sqrt{(1.3429 - 0.4049) \left(\frac{4 \times 8.08}{314.1593 \times 383} \right)}$$

$$t_{cr} = 0.0024s \cong 0.02s$$

Critical clearing time for Modified Euler solutions:

$$t_{cr} = \sqrt{(4.9471 - 0.4049) \left(\frac{4 \times 8.08}{314.1593 \times 383} \right)}$$

$$t_{cr} = 0.034s \cong 0.03s$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

- **Discussion of simulation Results**

Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5, show the simulation results of: the swinging behaviours of generators rotor angle, the generators bus voltage angles and generators bus frequency respectively, with respect to time at the instant of fault.

Figure 3: Generator Rotor Angle

Figure 4: Generator Bus Voltage Angle

Figure 5: Generator Bus Frequency

As shown in Figure 3, when a 3-phase fault initiated at Port Harcourt mains injection substation at time $t=0s$. Generators 19 and 20 accelerated to a power angle up to 82 degrees respectively, while generators 17 and 18 accelerated to a power angle of 97 and 65 degrees respectively.

As shown in Figure 4, it was observed that during fault, at time $t = 0s$, the generator terminal voltage angle suddenly rises up to 68 degree for bus 1, bus 2 and bus 3 respectively. When fault was cleared at 4 cycles, the fluctuation reduced gradually, and stable operating state was reached and the generator-maintained synchronism.

As shown in Figure 5, It was observed that during fault, starting from time $t = 0s$, the generator frequency rises up to 100.4% for bus 1, bus 2 and bus 3 respectively. When fault was cleared at 4 cycles, the oscillation reduced and a stable operating condition reached. The generators now maintained synchronism.

• **Numerical Methods Solutions**

Figure 6: Plot of Rotor Angle (rad) Versus Incremental Time(s).

The result as shown in Figure 6, indicated that the plot predicting the behaviour of the rotor angle (δ) with response to various time increase when a three phase was initiated using Trapezoidal rule method converges with the conventional swing equation technique. It implies that there is insignificant error between the conventional swing equation technique and the Trapezoidal rule method results. In contrary, the plot of the results of Modified Euler was diverging from the conventional swing equation technique results.

V. Conclusion

Total or partial system collapse can be minimized in power system if the transmission section stability is enhanced through accurate transient instability prediction in order to alert the operator to take necessary measures to prevent voltage collapse when the system is subjected to sudden and severe disturbances. This study carried out transient stability prediction on 132kV transmission grid power system using Trapezoidal rule technique. Simulation was carried out using Electrical Transient Analysis Program (ETAP) software. The Convectional Swing Equation method, Modified Euler Method and Trapezoidal rule technique were used to strongly estimate changes in rotor angles of the synchronous machines with respect to incremental time at the instant of fault. For transient stability analysis of the study case, the numerical solution obtained by Modified Euler and Trapezoidal methods was thoroughly compared with the necessary visualization and analysis error. It is concluded that Trapezoidal rule method has a good balance of efficiency and accuracy.

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APPENDIX A

Single Line Diagram of 132kV Afam to Port Harcourt Transmission Grid

Single Line Diagram of Afam Power Generating Station before Simulation